

ONE MODULO N GRACEFULNESS OF REGULAR BAMBOO TREE AND COCONUT TREE

V.Ramachandran¹ C.Sekar²

¹ Department of Mathematics, P.S.R Engineering College (Affiliated to Anna University
Chennai), Sevalpatti,
Sivakasi, Tamil Nadu, India.

² Department of Mathematics, Aditanar College of Arts and Science (Affiliated to MS
University Tirunelveli),
Tiruchendur, Tamil Nadu, India.

Abstract

A function f is called a graceful labelling of a graph G with q edges if f is an injection from the vertices of G to the set $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, q\}$ such that, when each edge xy is assigned the label $|f(x) - f(y)|$, the resulting edge labels are distinct. A graph G is said to be one modulo N graceful (where N is a positive integer) if there is a function f from the vertex set of G to $\{0, 1, N, (N + 1), 2N, (2N + 1), \dots, N(q - 1), N(q - 1) + 1\}$ in such a way that (i) f is 1-1 (ii) f induces a bijection ϕ from the edge set of G to $\{1, N + 1, 2N + 1, \dots, N(q - 1) + 1\}$ where $\phi(uv) = |f(u) - f(v)|$. In this paper we prove that the every regular bamboo tree and coconut tree are one modulo N graceful for all positive integers N .

1. INTRODUCTION

S.W.Golomb [2] introduced graceful labelling. Odd graceful was introduced by B.Gnanajothi [1]. C.Sekar [6] introduced one modulo three graceful labelling. V.Ramachandran and C.Sekar [4] introduced the concept of one modulo N graceful where N is any positive integer. In the case $N = 2$, the labelling is odd graceful and in the case $N = 1$ the labelling is graceful. [6] Every regular bamboo tree is graceful. In this paper we establish the result for one modulo N graceful ($N > 1$) of the regular bamboo tree and also we prove that coconut tree is one modulo N graceful for all positive integers N . In order to prove the existing conjecture

Problem 1. All trees are graceful?

Problem 2. All lobsters are graceful?

we take a diversion to prove one modulo N graceful of acyclic graphs. Sometimes the technique involved in one modulo N graceful labelling may yield a new approach to have graceful labelling of graphs. Our approach will motivate the scholars to do more research in this area.

2 Main Results Definition 2.1. A graph G with q edges is said to be one modulo N graceful (where N is a positive integer) if there is a function f from the vertex set of G to $\{0, 1, N, (N + 1), 2N, (2N + 1), \dots, N(q - 1), N(q - 1) + 1\}$ in such a way that (i) f is 1-1 (ii) f induces a bijection f_{uv} from the edge set of G to $\{1, N + 1, 2N + 1, \dots, N(q - 1) + 1\}$ where $f_{uv} = |f(u) - f(v)|$.

Definition 2.2. Consider k copies of paths P_n of length $n-1$ and stars S_m with m pendant vertices. Identify one of the two pendant vertices of the j th path with the centre of the j th star. Identify the other pendant vertex of each path with a single vertex u_0 (u_0 is not in any of the star and path). The graph obtained is a regular bamboo tree. Definition 2.3. A coconut Tree $CT(m, n)$ is the graph obtained from the path P_n by appending m new pendent edges at an end vertex of P_n .

Theorem 2.4. Every regular bamboo tree is one modulo N graceful for every positive integer $N > 1$.

Proof: Let $u_1^{(j)}, u_2^{(j)}, \dots, u_n^{(j)}$ be the vertices of the j th path where $u_1^{(j)}$ is identified with u_0 and $u_n^{(j)}$ is identified with $v_0^{(j)}$ which is the centre of the j th star. Let $v_1^{(j)}, v_2^{(j)}, \dots, v_m^{(j)}$ be the pendant vertices of the j th star. The bamboo tree has $k(n+m-1)+1$ vertices and $k(n+m-1)$ edges. Namin of the vertices is as shown in the figure.

Case (i) k is odd and n is odd
 Define

$$\phi(u_0) = \phi(u_1^{(j)}) = 0$$

For $i = 2, 4, \dots, n-1$

$$\phi(u_i^{(j)}) = Nk(n+m-1) - (N-1) - N(j-1) - \frac{Nk(i-2)}{2} \quad \text{for } j = 1, 2, \dots, k$$

For $i = 3, 5, \dots, n$

$$\phi(u_i^{(j)}) = \begin{cases} N(k+1) + N(j-1) + \frac{Nk(i-3)}{2} & \text{for } j = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{(k-1)}{2} \\ \frac{N(k+1)}{2} + N(j - \frac{(k+1)}{2}) + \frac{Nk(i-3)}{2} & \text{for } j = \frac{(k+1)}{2}, \frac{(k+3)}{2}, \dots, k \end{cases}$$

For $r = 1, 2, \dots, m$

$$\phi(v_r^{(j)}) = Nk(n+m-1) - (N-1) - \frac{Nk(n-1)}{2} - Nk(r-1) - N(j-1) \quad \text{for } j = 1, 2, \dots, k$$

From the definition of ϕ it is clear that

$$\{\phi(u_0)\} \cup \{\phi(u_i^{(j)}), i = 2, 3, \dots, n \text{ and } j = 1, 2, \dots, k\} \cup \{\phi(v_r^{(j)}), r = 1, 2, \dots, m \text{ and } j = 1, 2, \dots, k\} = \{0\} \cup \{Nk(n+m-1) - N + 1, Nk(n+m-2) - N + 1, \dots, Nk(\frac{n+2m+1}{2}) - N + 1, Nk(n+m-1) - 2N + 1, Nk(n+m-2) - 2N + 1, \dots, Nk(\frac{n+2m+1}{2}) - 2N + 1, \dots, Nk(n+m-2) + 1, Nk(n+m-3) + 1, \dots, Nk(\frac{n+2m-1}{2}) + 1\} \cup \{N(k+1), N(2k+1), \dots, Nk(\frac{n-1}{2}) + N, N(k+2), N(2k+2), \dots, Nk(\frac{n-1}{2}) + 2N, \dots, \frac{N}{2}(3k-1), \frac{N}{2}(5k-1), \dots, \frac{N}{2}(nk-1), \frac{N}{2}(k+1), \frac{N}{2}(3k+1), \dots, \frac{N}{2}(nk-k+1), \frac{N}{2}(k+3), \frac{N}{2}(3k+3), \dots, \frac{N}{2}(nk-2k+3), \dots, Nk, 2Nk, \dots, \frac{Nk}{2}(n-1)\} \cup \{\frac{Nk}{2}(n+2m-1) - N + 1, \frac{Nk}{2}(n+2m-3) - N + 1, \dots, \frac{Nk}{2}(n+1) - N + 1, \frac{Nk}{2}(n+2m-1) - 2N + 1, \frac{Nk}{2}(n+2m-3) - 2N + 1, \dots, \frac{Nk}{2}(n+1) - 2N + 1, \dots, \frac{Nk}{2}(n+2m-3) + 1, \frac{Nk}{2}(n+2m-5) + 1, \dots, \frac{Nk}{2}(n-1) + 1\}$$

Thus it is clear that the vertices have distinct labels. Therefore ϕ is 1-1.

We compute the edge labelling in the following sequence.

For $1 \leq j \leq k$

$$|\phi(u_2^{(j)}) - \phi(u_0)| = Nk(n+m-1) - Nj + 1$$

For $1 \leq r \leq m$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{k-1}{2}$

$$|\phi(v_r^{(j)}) - \phi(u_n^{(j)})| = Nk(m-r+1) - 2Nj + 1$$

For $1 \leq r \leq m$ and $j = \frac{k+1}{2}, \frac{k+3}{2}, \dots, k$

$$|\phi(v_r^{(j)}) - \phi(u_n^{(j)})| = Nk(m-r+2) - 2Nj + 1$$

For $j = 2, 4, \dots, n-1$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{k-1}{2}$

$$|\phi(u_i^{(j)}) - \phi(u_{i+1}^{(j)})| = Nk(n+m-i) - 2Nj + 1$$

For $j = 2, 4, \dots, n-1$ and $j = \frac{k+1}{2}, \frac{k+3}{2}, \dots, k$

$$|\phi(u_i^{(j)}) - \phi(u_{i+1}^{(j)})| = Nk(n+m-i+1) - 2Nj + 1$$

For $j = 3, 5, \dots, n-2$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{k-1}{2}$

$$|\phi(u_{i+1}^{(j)}) - \phi(u_i^{(j)})| = Nk(n+m-i) - 2Nj + 1$$

For $j = 3, 5, \dots, n-2$ and $j = \frac{k+1}{2}, \frac{k+3}{2}, \dots, k$

$$|\phi(u_{i+1}^{(j)}) - \phi(u_i^{(j)})| = Nk(n+m-i+1) - 2Nj + 1$$

This shows that the edges have the distinct labels $\{1, N+1, 2N+1, \dots, N(q-1)+1\}$.

It is clear from the above labelling that the function ϕ from the vertex set of G to $\{0, 1, N, (N + 1), 2N, (2N + 1), \dots, N(q - 1), N(q - 1) + 1\}$ is in such a way that (i) ϕ is 1-1 (ii) ϕ induces a bijection ϕ^* from the edge set of G to $\{1, N + 1, 2N + 1, \dots, N(q - 1) + 1\}$ where $\phi^*(uv) = |\phi(u) - \phi(v)|$. Hence the regular bamboo tree is one modulo N graceful.

Clearly ϕ defines a one modulo N graceful labelling of regular bamboo tree.

Example 2.5. One modulo 5 graceful labelling of regular bamboo tree. ($k = 5, n = 5, m = 3$)

Case (ii) k is odd and n is even
Define

$$\phi(u_0) = \phi(u_1^{(j)}) = 0$$

For $i = 2, 4, \dots, n$

$$\phi(u_i^{(j)}) = Nk(n + m - 1) - (N - 1) - N(j - 1) - \frac{Nk(i-2)}{2} \quad \text{for } j = 1, 2, \dots, k$$

For $i = 3, 5, \dots, n - 1$

$$\phi(u_i^{(j)}) = \begin{cases} N(k + 1) + N(j - 1) + \frac{Nk(i-3)}{2} & \text{for } j = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{(k-1)}{2} \\ \frac{N(k+1)}{2} + N(j - \frac{(k+1)}{2}) + \frac{Nk(i-3)}{2} & \text{for } j = \frac{(k+1)}{2}, \frac{(k+3)}{2}, \dots, k \end{cases}$$

For $r = 1, 2, \dots, m$

$$\phi(v_r^{(j)}) = \begin{cases} \frac{N(kn+2)}{2} + Nk(r - 1) + N(j - 1) & \text{for } j = 1, 2, \dots, \frac{(k-1)}{2} \\ \frac{N(k(n-1)+1)}{2} + Nk(r - 1) + N(j - \frac{(k+2)}{2}) & \text{for } j = \frac{(k+1)}{2}, \frac{(k+3)}{2}, \dots, k \end{cases}$$

The proof is similar to the proof in case(i).

Clearly ϕ defines a one modulo N graceful labelling of regular bamboo tree.

Example 2.6. One modulo 8 graceful labelling of regular bamboo tree. ($k = 3, n = 6, m = 2$)

Case (iii) k is even and n is odd
Define

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(v_r^{(1)}) &= N(r-1) \quad \text{for } r = 1, 2, \dots, m \\ \phi(u_0) &= Nk(n+m-1) - (N-1) - \frac{N(n-1)}{2} \\ \phi(u_i^{(1)}) &= \begin{cases} N(m-1) + \frac{N(n-1)}{2} - \frac{N(i-2)}{2} & \text{for } i = 2, 4, \dots, n-1 \\ Nk(m+n-1) + 1 - \frac{N(n-1)}{2} + \frac{N(i-3)}{2} & \text{for } i = 3, 5, \dots, n \end{cases} \\ \text{For } i = 3, 5, \dots, n \\ \phi(u_i^{(j)}) &= Nk(n+m-1) - (N-1) - N(j-2) - \frac{N(n-1+k)}{2} - \frac{N(k-1)(i-3)}{2} \quad \text{for } j = 2, 3, \dots, k \\ \text{For } i = 2, 4, \dots, n-1 \\ \phi(u_i^{(j)}) &= \begin{cases} Nm + \frac{N(n-1+k)}{2} + N(j-2) + \frac{N(k-1)(i-2)}{2} & \text{for } j = 2, 3, \dots, \frac{k}{2} \\ N(m-1) + \frac{N(n-1)}{2} + N + N(j - \frac{k}{2} - 1) + \frac{N(k-1)(i-2)}{2} & \text{for } j = \frac{k}{2} + 1, \frac{k}{2} + 2, \dots, k \end{cases} \\ \text{For } r = 1, 2, \dots, m \\ \phi(v_r^{(j)}) &= \begin{cases} Nm + \frac{N(n-1+k)}{2} + N(j-2) + \frac{N(k-1)(n-3)}{2} + N(k-1) + N(k-1)(r-1) & \text{for } j = 2, 3, \dots, \frac{k}{2} \\ Nm + \frac{N(n-1)}{2} + \frac{N(k-1)(n-3)}{2} + N(k-1) + N(j - \frac{k}{2} - 1) + N(k-1)(r-1) & \text{for } j = \frac{k}{2} + 1, \dots, k \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

The proof is similar to the proof in case(i).

Clearly defines a one modulo N graceful labelling of regular bamboo tree.

Example 2.7. One modulo 5 graceful labelling of regular bamboo tree. (k = 6, n = 7, m = 3)

Case (iv) k is even and n is even

Define

$$\phi(v_r^{(1)}) = N(r-1) \quad \text{for } r = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

$$\phi(u_0) = N(m-1) - \frac{Nn}{2}$$

$$\phi(u_i^{(1)}) = \begin{cases} Nk(m+n-1) - (N-1) - \frac{N(n-2)}{2} + \frac{N(i-2)}{2} & \text{for } i = 2, 4, \dots, n \\ N(m-1) + \frac{N(n-2)}{2} - \frac{N(i-3)}{2} & \text{for } i = 3, 5, \dots, n-1 \end{cases}$$

For $i = 2, 4, \dots, n$

$$\phi(u_i^{(j)}) = Nk(n+m-1) - (2N-1) - N(j-2) - \frac{N(n-2)}{2} - \frac{N(k-1)(i-2)}{2} \quad \text{for } j = 2, 3, \dots, k$$

For $i = 3, 5, \dots, n-1$

$$\phi(u_i^{(j)}) = \begin{cases} Nm + \frac{N(n+k)}{2} + N(j-2) + N(\frac{k}{2}-1) + \frac{N(k-1)(i-3)}{2} & \text{for } j = 2, 3, \dots, \frac{k}{2} \\ Nm + \frac{N(n+k)}{2} + N(j - \frac{k}{2} - 1) + \frac{N(k-1)(i-3)}{2} & \text{for } j = \frac{k}{2} + 1, \frac{k}{2} + 2, \dots, k \end{cases}$$

For $r = 1, 2, \dots, m$

$$\phi(v_r^{(j)}) = \begin{cases} Nm + \frac{N(n+k)}{2} + N(j-2) + \frac{N(k-1)(n-4)}{2} + N(\frac{k}{2}-2) + N(k-1)(r-1) & \text{for } j = 2, 3, \dots, \frac{k}{2} \\ Nm + \frac{N(n+k)}{2} + N(k-1)(n-4) + N(k-2) + N(j - \frac{k}{2} - 1) + N(k-1)(r-1) & \text{for } j = \frac{k}{2} + 1, \dots, k \end{cases}$$

The proof is similar to the proof in case(i).

Clearly defines a one modulo N graceful labelling of regular bamboo tree.

Example 2.8. One modulo 10 graceful labelling of regular bamboo tree. ($k = 8, n = 6, m = 2$)

Theorem 2.9. *Coconut tree is one modulo N graceful for every positive integer N .*

Proof: Let u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n be the vertices of a path P_n and v_1, v_2, \dots, v_m be the pendent vertices being adjacent with u_1 in the coconut tree G . Let e_i denote the edge $u_i u_{i+1}$ of P_n for $1 < i < n - 1$ and $u_1 v_i$ for $1 \leq i \leq m$. The coconut tree G has $m + n$ vertices and $m + n - 1$ edges.

Case (i) n is odd.

Let $n = 2k + 1$, $k > 1$.

Define

$$\phi(u_{2i-1}) = N(i-1) \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k+1$$

$$\phi(u_{2i}) = 2Nk - (N-1) - N(i-1) \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k$$

$$\phi(v_i) = 2Nk + 1 + N(i-1) \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$$

From the definition of ϕ it is clear that

$$\{\phi(u_i), i = 1, 2, \dots, n\} \cup \{\phi(v_i), i = 1, 2, \dots, m\} = \{0, N, 2N, \dots, Nk\} \cup \{N(2k-1) + 1, N(2k-2) + 1, \dots, Nk + 1\} \cup \{N(2k) + 1, N(2k+1) + 1, \dots, N(2k+m-1) + 1\}$$

Thus it is clear that the vertices have distinct labels. Therefore ϕ is 1-1.

We compute the edge labelling in the following sequence.

For $1 \leq i \leq m$

$$|\phi(v_i) - \phi(u_1)| = N(2k + i - 1) + 1$$

For $1 \leq i \leq k$

$$|\phi(u_{2i}) - \phi(u_{2i-1})| = N(2k + 1 - 2i) + 1$$

$$|\phi(u_{2i}) - \phi(u_{2i+1})| = N(2k - 2i) + 1$$

This shows that the edges have the distinct labels $\{1, N + 1, 2N + 1, \dots, N(q - 1) + 1\}$.

It is clear from the above labelling that the function ϕ from the vertex set of G to $\{0, 1, N, (N + 1), 2N, (2N + 1), \dots, N(q - 1), N(q - 1) + 1\}$ is in such a way that (i) ϕ is 1-1 (ii) ϕ induces a bijection ϕ^* from the edge set of G to $\{1, N + 1, 2N + 1, \dots, N(q - 1) + 1\}$ where $\phi^*(uv) = |\phi(u) - \phi(v)|$. Hence the coconut tree is one modulo N graceful.

Clearly ϕ defines a one modulo N graceful labelling of coconut tree.

Example 2.10. *One modulo 3 graceful labelling and graceful labelling of coconut tree*

Case (ii) n is even.

Let $n = 2k$.

Define

$$\phi(u_{2i-1}) = N(i-1) \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k$$

$$\phi(u_{2i}) = 2Nk - (2N - 1) - N(i-1) \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k$$

$$\phi(v_i) = 2Nk + 1 + N(i-1) \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$$

The proof is similar to the proof in case(i).

Clearly ϕ defines a one modulo N graceful labelling of coconut tree.

Example 2.11. *One modulo 10 graceful labelling and odd graceful labelling of coconut tree.*

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